

THE LOGISTIC METHOD AND THE GENESIS OF RELIGIONS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the role and importance of the logistic method in the origin and development of religions. The limitations of historicism in the study of this phenomenon are shown.

Keywords: religion, religious studies, the genesis of religion, faith, conviction.

The object that the science of religious studies studies is a social phenomenon – religion, which has a specific genesis (origin), historical forms, a specific appearance and name in different spaces and times. The word religion means faith, conviction, chastity, trust, reward, condemnation. We will formulate our specific thoughts and judgments based on the study of the concepts of "Faith" and "Belief", which represent a wide range of meanings. The concepts of "faith" and "belief" are categories of philosophical cognition - epistemology. Based on the fact that a person is a social being, the satisfaction of his biological needs (of a living being) that ensure his existence. From a philosophical point of view, the difference between a person and an animal is that he has a mind, thinking, while according to the theory of cultural studies, a person creates, produces, creates from nature what is necessary for material existence, and objects with his own hands and mind. This suggests that a person is a sociocultural being.

Along with biological (eating, drinking, clothing and housing) and physiological (sleep, rest) needs, there are spiritual human needs, according to which, collectively, a person will have the status of a social being, a pearl of this universe and a saint. A spiritual need is a need for knowledge about nature and society, as well as about oneself. This need is called an epistemological need. The process of cognition has the forms of sensation, perception, and representation.

Formation of concepts about the content and essence of things and things through them, mutual cause-effect, necessary connections. This is the highest knowledge. Various aspects of human existence are autonomous, not a "product". The diversity of needs has given rise to what we call forms of social consciousness, such as science, philosophy, religion, ethics, art, society and law. There are basic fundamental conditions that apply to the knowledge consumed. First of all, this knowledge must be correct and true, without internal

contradictions and discrepancies, in a word, a clear perception of the object that they reflect. Because people need knowledge "not for the sake of erudition", but for the sake of application in their practical activities, their tasks, their mastery and transformation of the external world. The second condition is that people should trust them so that they can build on the true knowledge they have acquired. Thanks to trust, it is achieved that new knowledge does not contradict previous ones, matching, filling, expanding and deepening experience, skills, dexterity and knowledge. Because no matter how real they are, a person does not use them in practice if he does not believe them. Faith, in turn, is a criterion of humanity and spiritual perfection. Some people (even scientists) cannot know for sure the degree of reliability of all knowledge, cannot be proved by evidence and experience, experiment, scientific laws, so they trust in trust. Unfortunately, religious dogmas are an example of this. The root of such views is the juxtaposition of secular and religious sciences, and science and religion are actually an inability to recognize that the sciences are unified and integral.

The concept of "faith" is referred to in Islam as – Iman." Turning to the above-mentioned, let's focus on the question of the genesis (origin) of religions. Since its inception, humanity has carried out on the basis of simple, uncomplicated tools, mainly manual force, and a narrow, uncomplicated, limited imagination and concepts of the world that surrounded themselves, very far from realizing the leprosy of things and actions.

Dependence on nature (the wealth of fauna and flora), impotence and fear caused by a misunderstanding of the natural hosts, have been trying for several tens of thousands of years to satisfy the needs that were able to explore the universe (albeit narrow), while satisfying their material exhausted themselves and began to expand the stock of knowledge. We can observe a person's growth from the very birth of a child in order to imagine the path they have traveled. The main question that a child asks out of 2-3 questions is "What is it?" It is a desire to know certain things and objects, to satisfy an epistemological need. When a child turns 4-5 years old, he moves on to the next stage after acquiring certain initial and primary knowledge, and now – "Why?" seeks to know the structure, cause-effect and necessary relationships of objects and physical evidence by asking a question. Thus, until he reaches an age, becoming a person accumulates humanity in the process, and satisfies his epistemological needs through knowledge. If 15-20 years are enough for this, then humanity has spent several thousand years trying to turn this stock - summing up for consumption. In this process, we must feel the service of our ancestors and their contribution,

we must thank them, we must practice them and gratefully accept the spiritual riches that they have left.

We have the opportunity to acquire this knowledge in the short term. In the field of knowledge that humanity has accumulated, assimilated, memorized, used, the balance, value and place of religious knowledge in the world of knowledge are incomparable. Religious sciences should first of all be understood as sacred books, teachings, creeds of (currently) existing world religions (Islam, Christianity, Buddhism) and national religions (Hinduism, Judaism). Today there are few adherents of Zoroastrianism, Monism, Mazdakism, Shintoism, Confucianism, Taoism, Jainism, etc.). The teachings of religions are also the basis of religious sciences. The science of religion, which is considered a spiritual and cultural wealth, the values of human civilization, immaculate and incomparable, is a wonderful social worker. Although religion has a history of several thousand years, less than 200 years have passed since the advent of the science of religious studies, which studies it. In the formation of this science, the main place is occupied by the disciplines of philosophy, anthropology, ethnography, archaeology, linguistics, mythology and folklore studies, which studied various aspects of humanity and society. The role of factual materials collected by such disciplines as anthropology, ethnography, and archaeology in the study of the processes of genesis and evolutionary transformation of religions is incomparable. Assuming that mythological thinking was the first form of contemplation of the world, the highest historical stages of cognition – religious and scientific thought, the basis, the fundamental basis of the place of mythology, comparisons and morality become more obvious.

The knowledge accumulated by various fields of science, which is the source of religious studies, also serves to assess the historical forms of religions. When it comes to historical forms of religions, primitive religions or clan-tribal religions, national religions and religions of the world are mentioned. It is possible to clarify knowledge about the first forms of religion, assuming that the primitive social chaos of mankind has a history of several tens of thousands of years. To represent the religious landscape of this period, it is possible to distinguish the stages of primitive religious ideas and tribal religions-germs. When studying ancient history, we are faced with a shortage of resources and materials. The method of historicism is based on the facts of history, ethnography, archaeology, anthropology and other sciences. We are aware that this resource is limited. This is a critical, limiting, deficit-saving, superficial method - logic. Using the method of logic, we will have the opportunity to study

the internal connections between social events and phenomena, causal and necessary connections, the emergence of social phenomena in a legitimate way. Early primitive religious beliefs included fetishism, totemism, animism, magic, and shamanism. Whether these forms appeared at the same time, whether there is a certain sequence, if any, which of them appeared earlier, which later, I think that questions about the reason are justified. The answer to these questions should have a logical justification (we believe that it is impossible to obtain historically reliable information for the reason mentioned above). Since man lived in nature, natural phenomena and objects, as well as natural objects, directly influenced the lifestyle that he defined. The inconveniences associated with the natural simplicity of life (characteristics of the area, climatic conditions, diversity of plants and animals, etc.) have given rise to ideas about fetishism and totemism. This was also the result of using natural jumpers. For example, the alternation of day and night is the alternation of innocence and darkness. It was in them that the fear was strong that the darkness was a danger to the human. The realization that human existence consists of the unity of his body and soul is what gave rise to animistic visions in the process (based on the understanding that the life force is also characteristic of flora and fauna). This is the highest stage of religious imagination. This indicates that animistic ideas persist in the national religions emerging at that time, including the religions of Hinduism (in certain systematic views on immortality, the resurrection of souls). The most basic, primary reason for the hope and aspiration (worship, sacrifice) for the existence of supernatural forces inherent in early religious visions is the smallness, narrowness of human knowledge about natural phenomena, that is—epistemological hunger.

Belief in supernatural powers causes them to worship, with various rituals arising from the worship. The religious visions of magicians and shamanism are aimed at salvation (mainly healing from diseases in shamanism) through supernatural forces. Of course, this sequence is relative, in a broad sense it is a product of the primitive era. Another idea. The cult of zinc's ancestors and forms of worship of tribal leaders-seeds (later, in national state religions, horns, pharaohs, so-called heads of state) should be attributed to the above-mentioned primitive religious beliefs. Clan-tribal religions can be considered as a reflexive higher stage representing evolutionism, a relatively primitive system of their primitive religious ideas. Based on the meaning of the word "faith", it is possible to classify religions based on the answer to the question of what (regardless of when and where) is believed, what is the object of faith. Based on the above

examples, we can show fetishistic (natural material things), animistic (zinc, soul, that is, immaterial) religions. As religions developed and improved as social media, the sphere of knowledge expanded, the idea that the creator of the material and immaterial world, Theos (God), later became doctrines, that is, theistic religions appeared. Typical of the clan-tribal era, the gods were a continuation of primitive representations, fetishes and totems with their objects in the form of stones, trees, metal, clay idols. When logically considering the creator, the protective force can be interpreted as being in the material couriers, the stage of communion with the level of the divine (pagan) Of god. As an illustration of what we have said, we consider it appropriate to cite the opinions of the authors of the book "The History of Islam" about the origin of the religious landscape in Arabia before the advent of Islam. Claiming that idolatry was a new phase of religion, it is said that there were certain settlements in different parts of Arabia that were considered places of pilgrimage. The most famous of the Quraish sanams was Hubal. It was made of carnelian (a red semi-precious stone) in the shape of a man without a right hand, to which the Quraish attached a golden brush. We know that 360 idols inside and outside the Kaaba, which became the Sanam pantheon when the city of Mecca was conquered in 630, were smashed. Dedicated to the Arab polytheism of Ibn al-Kalbi, the book is the title of the first 5 Sanams mentioned in Al-asnom (Wadd, Suvo', Yogus, Yuk, Nasr) mentioned in the Quran by Ham (verses 22-23 of Surah Nuks). Wadd is a male figure, Suvo'el is a man, Yog is a Lion, Yuk is a horse and a prosaic Eagle. Manot, the oldest surviving Sanam mentioned in the Quran. In the Jahili Arabic view, these three were gods.

Religions are divided into polytheistic and monotheistic religions. From polytheism to monotheism (and not vice versa), it should be assumed that the direction of the development of the Universe and human cognition corresponds to a process whose tendency has an internal logic. The history of religions testifies to the existence of an intermediate view – genotheism - during the transition from polytheism to monotheism. Genotheism is a belief in polytheism, but one of them is the view that the main God is the main God. For example, among the inhabitants (gods) of Mount Olympus, we can see the status of the god Zeus. The historical presence of this form corresponds to logic. The conclusion is that using the method of logism, along with historicism, in presenting the history of religions, helps to understand the problem comprehensively and deeply.

References:

1. Sheikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf- Myminning merozhi. Vol.: 2015, p. 6.
2. History of Islam. A.Khasanov et al., 2007. pp. 60-61.
3. Турдиев, Б. (2024). JAMIYAT IDEOSFERASINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 4(2).
4. Турдиев, Б. (2023). IBN SINONING HUQUQIY TA'LIMOTLAR RIVOJIDA QO 'SHGAN HISSASI. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 3(S/3), 214-220.
5. Turdiyev, B. S. (2023). KONFUTSIYNING SIYOSIY- HUQUQIY TA'LIMOT RIVOJIGA QO 'SHGAN HISSASI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(21), 519-522.
6. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Manifestations of Moral Threats in the Ideosphere of Uzbekistan and Their Prevention Strategy. Asian Journal of Basic Science & Research, 5(1), 103-108.
7. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST), 7(1), 149-157.
8. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Civil Society and its Influence in Society's Ideosphere. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 4(12), 84-89.
9. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). MANIFESTATION OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE IDEOSPHERE OF UZBEKISTAN. Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects, 89-92.
10. Sobirovich, T. B., & Norman, Z. D. M. (2023). Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan. Harmony, 7(1), 08-16.
11. Turdiyev, B. S. (2022). INTERPRETATION OF UNIVERSAL VALUES IN ZOROASTRIANISM. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 109-114. Sobirovich, T. B. Interethnic Harmony And Religious Tolerance- An Integral Part of The Ancient Traditions Of The Uzbeks.
12. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 1. – С. 334-338.

13. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 9. – С. 197-202.
14. Sobirovich T. B. Issues of gender equality in uzbekistan: Strategy of reforms //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 9. – С. 203-207.
15. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 3. – С. 131-135.
16. Sobirovich T. B. Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development //Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IIJSR). – 2021.
17. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 229-233.
18. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 122-126.
19. Sobirovich T. B., Murodogli I. S. The strategy for the implementation of the modern governance system in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 5. – С. 741-748.